

Oral Cavity: The Mirror of Health

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Abstract

Oral health is essential as it symbolizes the overall health, well-being and quality of life of an individual. Many systemic diseases have oral manifestations. while sometimes oral signs and symptoms are the first and even the only evidence of a disturbed state. The mouth and face are highly accessible parts of the body, sensitive to and able to reflect changes occurring internally. If the integrity of oral tissues is compromised, mouth can become a source of disease or pathological processes affecting other parts of the body. Relationship between oral and general health has been increasingly recognized in the recent years. Various nutritional deficiencies have oral manifestations and needs to looked for in urgency as it affects the overall health of the individual and can have serious long-term effects. Autoimmune diseases have the tendency of not recovering fully, though not fatal. Quality of life depends on alleviation of oral and systemic signs and symptoms. Endocrine disorders work at hormonal levels and exhibit wide variety of oral manifestations. Relation of dermatological diseases and oral manifestations are known since decades and patients are referred to dentist for oral manifestations. Oral lesions are reported in many psychiatric disorders and dentists may be the first health care provider to assess the conditions. Also, neoplastic lesions may metastases to jaw, oral soft tissues and if not aware of these manifestations can lead to diagnostic dilemma. Thus, Dentists must be familiar with systemic conditions that can affect the oral cavity, so that appropriate referral can be made.

Introduction

Oral health is essential as it symbolizes the overall health, well-being and quality of life of an individual, thus oral cavity is rightly described as a mirror of general health or diseases. ⁽¹⁾ Also, it can be called early warning system. As the gateway to the body, a constant barrage of invaders like bacteria, viruses, parasites, and fungi, challenges the oral cavity.

Many systemic diseases have oral manifestations. while sometimes the oral signs and symptoms are the first and even the only evidence of a disturbed state e.g. Koplik's spots in the buccal mucosa which precede the cutaneous eruption of measles.

In other cases, the oral symptoms and/or signs may parallel the complaints and symptoms elsewhere in the body.

The simultaneous development of an erosive lesion on the buccal mucosa near the angle of lips along with a butterfly rash on the face is presumptive of lupus erythematosus.

The oral manifestations follow the evidence in other parts of the body, like in pemphigus, where the bullae may erupt on the skin days, weeks, or months before the oral ulcers can be demonstrated.

These oral appearances must be properly recognized if the patient is to receive appropriate diagnosis and referral for treatment.

Thus, oral cavity is an important diagnostic area not just because it contains derivatives of all of the primary germinal layers, and includes tissues not demonstrable elsewhere in the body, but also because of its role played in diagnosing a number of systemic diseases just because of their oral manifestations.

The mouth and face are highly accessible parts of the body, sensitive to and able to reflect changes occurring internally.

In the event that the integrity of the oral tissues is compromised, the mouth can become a source of disease or pathological processes affecting other parts of the body. ⁽²⁾

The relationship between oral and general health has been increasingly recognized in the recent years.

Several epidemiological studies have linked poor oral health with cardiovascular disease, poor glycaemic control in diabetics, low birth-weight pre-term babies, and a number of other conditions, including rheumatoid arthritis and osteoporosis. ⁽²⁾

Oral infections are also recognized as a problem for individuals suffering from a range of chronic conditions, including cancer and HIV virus. The oral cavity can be considered as a window to the body because many important systemic disorders manifest in the oral cavity.

The dentist is frequently the first medical person to encounter such disorders. These oral manifestations must be properly recognized if the patient is to receive appropriate diagnosis and referral for treatment.

This review article focuses on the various systemic diseases and their oral manifestations.

NUTRITIONAL DEFICIENCIES

Due to rapid cell turnover of the oral mucosa, nutritional deficiencies may present first with oral manifestations. Changes may occur in the tongue papillae, mucosal color and integrity, and also in the oral sensation.

- **Vitamin A**

- ✓ Tooth eruption rate is retarded ⁽³⁾
- ✓ Retarded alveolar bone formation
- ✓ Hyperplastic gingival epithelium followed by keratinization.
- ✓ Inadequate cell differentiation- impaired healing & tissue regeneration, desquamation of oral mucosa, keratosis, increased risk of candidiasis. ⁽⁴⁾
- ✓ Gingival hypertrophy & inflammation,
- ✓ Leukoplakia.
- ✓ Decreased taste sensitivity, xerostomia, disturbed or arrested enamel development, irregular tubular dentine formation and increased caries risk. ⁽³⁾

- **Vitamin C deficiency (Scurvy)**

- ✓ Among the presenting features of scurvy, oral signs may be cardinal: fetid odour, and loosened teeth with 'swollen, tender, spongy bleeding - putrid gums'.
- ✓ Inflammation of the interdental and marginal gingiva followed by bleeding, ulceration, halitosis due to fusospirochetal stomatitis.⁽⁵⁾
- ✓ Hemorrhages into and swelling of the periodontal membranes occur, followed by loss of bone and loosening of the teeth, which eventually exfoliate.
- ✓ In fully developed scurvy the gingivae are 'boggy, ulcerated and bleed with the interdental and marginal gingiva becoming bright red, smooth, swollen and shiny.'⁽⁶⁾
- ✓ The gingiva become hyperaemic with a tendency to bleed easily on the interdental papillae, where disintegration of the marginal epithelium occurs.
- ✓ Secondary infection occurs and necrosis with ulceration develops.
- ✓ Alveolar bone resorption, with loosening and loss of teeth. The entire gum (i.e. the free gingival margin, the masticatory mucosa and the alveolar mucosa) may appear swollen, purplish and ulcerated. ⁽³⁾
- ✓ Chronic periodontitis characterized by microbial colonization of plaque on adjacent tooth surfaces extending into deeper periodontal tissue. ⁽⁶⁾
- ✓ This results in pocket formation, destruction of alveolar bone, tooth mobility and their eventual exfoliation.

- **Vitamin D**

- ✓ Developmental anomalies of dentin and enamel
- ✓ Delayed eruption and misalignment of the teeth in the jaws ⁽⁷⁾
- Vitamin D resistant rickets:- Only after the use of vitamin D in the treatment of rickets became widespread, it was found that this treatment strategy was not helping some patients even when vitamin D was used at the therapeutic dosage level. ⁽⁸⁾ These patients turned out to have what has been termed vitamin D-resistant rickets.
- ✓ Such patients typically have an unusually short stature, with the lower body segment and the lower limbs shortened and bowed. ⁽³⁾
- ✓ Dental findings include teeth with large pulp chambers, and pulp horns extending almost to the dentino-enamel junction.⁽⁹⁾Also, attrition causes the cuspal enamel to be worn down to the level of the pulp horn eventually causing pulpal exposure and pulp necrosis.

- ✓ These exposures are small in size, and periapical abscesses and gingival sinus tracts may be formed that appear to affect normal teeth.⁽⁹⁾
- ✓ Development of microclefts in the enamel may occur, allowing passage of oral microflora into the dentinal tubules and ultimately into the pulp.
- ✓ Radiographically, there is abnormal alveolar bone pattern, cementum, and lamina dura around the teeth is absent or poorly defined.
- **Vitamin K**
- ✓ Most common oral manifestation is gingival bleeding.⁽³⁾
- ✓ Prothrombin levels below 35% result in bleeding after tooth brushing; and when below 20% result in spontaneous gingival hemorrhages.⁽¹⁰⁾
- **Hypophosphatasia**
- ✓ Hypophosphatasia is a rare metabolic bone disease and is thought to be of an autosomal recessive trait pattern.⁽¹¹⁾
- ✓ The most important and one of the first presenting signs may be the premature loss of the primary teeth, particularly due to the lack of cementum on the root surfaces, and this occurs in the clinical setting inspite of lack of significant inflammatory response.⁽¹²⁾
- ✓ The deciduous incisor teeth are usually affected first and may be the only teeth involved. In some patients, this may be the only expression of the disease.
- ✓ In general, the severity of the condition is age dependent and the younger the age of onset, the more severe is the expression of the disease.⁽¹²⁾
- ✓ Bony abnormalities that resemble rickets may also be noted.⁽¹³⁾
- **Riboflavin deficiency**
- ✓ Initially glossitis involving the tip and/or the lateral margins of the tongue, followed later by complete atrophy of all papillae.⁽¹⁴⁾
- ✓ The tongue has a magenta color.⁽¹⁵⁾
- ✓ Pallor, involving oral mucosa followed by cheilosis, maceration and fissuring at the angles of the mouth.

AUTOIMMUNE CONDITIONS

- **Sjogren Syndrome**
- ✓ Sjogren syndrome (SS) is an autoimmune disease, affecting mostly women aged 50 years or older, characterized by Sicca syndrome or the “primary Sjogren,” comprising xerophthalmia and xerostomia.⁽¹⁵⁾
- ✓ These SS patients frequently present with a parotid gland enlargement.
- ✓ The secondary form of SS is often associated with another concurrent autoimmune disease, mostly rheumatoid arthritis (RA) or systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE).
- ✓ The oral manifestations in SS are generally related to the low salivary volume and comprise dysphagia, dysgeusia, difficulty in eating and speaking, as well as an increased rate of dental caries and susceptibility to infection.⁽¹⁵⁾
- ✓ The saliva is characteristically thick, ropery, and mucinous, or in some severe cases totally absent.⁽¹⁶⁾
- ✓ The mucosal changes related to xerostomia include dry, red, and wrinkled mucosa.

- ✓ The tongue may appear “bald” or even “cobblestone-like” due to atrophy of the papilla. Cracks, fissures of the tongue, redness, and cheilitis are additional findings.⁽¹⁶⁾
- ✓ *Candida albicans* is common.
- ✓ Relatively high incidence of dental caries because the decreased salivary flow rate.
- ✓ Dental caries is especially noted around the cervical region of the teeth.
- ✓ Inflammation of the parotid gland is a likely complication and is usually accompanied with fever and purulent discharge.
- **Kawasaki Disease**
- ✓ Kawasaki disease, also known as mucocutaneous lymph node syndrome, is a systemic vasculitis that affects medium- and large-sized arteries and lymph nodes, and is now considered to be the primary cause of childhood heart disease.⁽¹⁷⁾
- ✓ An episode of acute edema, erythema of the hands and feet, pyrexia, oral erythema, and multiple rashes are almost always observed.
- ✓ A diagnostic criterion requires that the body temperature must exceed 38.5⁰ C for minimum of 5 days.
- ✓ At least four of these five criteria have to be met to diagnose Kawasaki disease: (1) edema of extremity, erythema; (2) polymorphous exanthem; (3) bilateral conjunctival infection; (4) erythema and strawberry tongue; and (5) acute cervical lymphadenopathy.⁽¹⁷⁾
- ✓ The most striking oral finding includes swelling of papillae on the surface of the tongue (strawberry tongue) and intense erythema of the mucosal surfaces.
- ✓ The lips may be cracked, red, swollen, and often haemorrhagic and crusted.⁽¹⁸⁾
- **Scleroderma (Progressive Systemic Sclerosis; Hide-Bound Disease)**
- ✓ Scleroderma is a rare immunologically mediated condition characterized by deposition of extraordinary amounts of dense collagen in the tissues of the body.⁽¹⁵⁾
- ✓ Skin is commonly involved, but almost all body organs eventually are affected.
- ✓ When exposed to cold temperatures these patients show what is termed ‘Raynaud phenomenon’ in their terminal phalanges.
- ✓ The blood supply to the fingers or toes, and in some cases the nose or earlobes, is reduced, the skin turns pale or white, and numb, and with further depletion of oxygen supply the skin turns blue and cyanotic
- ✓ The face appears smooth, taut, stretched, and mask-like, due to subcutaneous collagen deposition.
- ✓ The “ala” of the nose becomes atrophic and exhibits a pinched appearance called “mouse facies.”⁽¹⁹⁾
- ✓ Oral manifestations are variable. The lips appear pursed due to constriction of the mouth, thus making it difficult to open the mouth and resulting in what is termed microstomia, causing limited opening of mouth in about 70% of these patients.
- ✓ A “purse-string” appearance caused by creases and folds of skin radiating from the mouth may be noted.⁽¹⁹⁾
- ✓ Xerostomia is a consistent finding, and some of these patients have concurrent secondary SS.
- ✓ The tongue can lose mobility and generally has a smooth appearance.
- ✓ The collagen deposits invariably result in smoothening of the palatal rugae.

- ✓ Diffuse widening of the periodontal ligament space is noted in the entire dentition. The mandible exhibits resorption of posterior part of the ramus, the coronoid process, the chin, and condyles on panoramic radiographs.
- **Systemic Lupus Erythematosus**
- ✓ SLE is an immunologically mediated condition and has multiple clinical presentations.
- ✓ In SLE, apart from the renal and cardiac involvement, oral lesions are noted in 5% to 25% of the patients.
- ✓ The lesions affect the palate, buccal mucosa, and the gingivae and may present as lichenoid areas that may be nonspecific in appearance, or even sometimes appear granulomatous.⁽¹⁵⁾
- ✓ “Lupus cheilitis” involving the lower lip vermilion may be noted. Oral ulceration, pain, erythema, and hyperkeratosis as well as complaints of stomatodynia, dysgeusia, xerostomia, candidiasis, and periodontal disease are noted with some frequency in patients with SLE.⁽²⁰⁾
- ✓ Chronic cutaneous lupus erythematosus (CCLE) is limited to the skin and is also known as discoid lupus erythematosus (DLE).
- ✓ In this category^{the} oral lesions are clinically identical to erosive lichen planus but these oral lesions are notably absent in the absence of skin lesions.
- ✓ Oral lesions are characteristically ulcerated, atrophic, and erythematous, exhibiting a central zone surrounded by white, fine, radiating striae that are often multiple.⁽²⁰⁾
- ✓ Sometimes these may show a central stippled white dotted area. These oral lesions may be painful when exposed to acidic or salty foods in particular.
- **Rheumatoid arthritis**
- ✓ The temporomandibular joint (TMJ) is often involved in rheumatoid arthritis. This is usually characterized by erosions in the condyle leading to a decreased range of motion of the mandible with pain upon movement.⁽¹⁵⁾
- ✓ Oral dryness and salivary gland swelling can also be found in patients with rheumatoid arthritis.
- ✓ The condition usually is not as severe as in the other joints that are involved but symptoms may include stiffness, crepitation, pain or ache.⁽²¹⁾
- ✓ The limited jaw function may necessitate TMJ reconstruction once the active disease is controlled.
- ✓ Gross destruction of the mandibular condyle may lead to mandibular micrognathia that presents with a receding chin and distinct malocclusion.
- ✓ Radiographically, the condylar head may appear flattened with irregular surface features, and the temporal fossa surface may be eroded and exhibit some remodelling.⁽²¹⁾
- ✓ Many of these patients also have secondary SS.

ENDOCRINE DISORDERS

- ✓ Oral manifestations may result from abnormal hormonal regulation.
- ✓ Sex hormone imbalance can result in marked reaction to local irritations of oral tissues. Changes resemble gingivitis and periodontitis, with marked inflammatory reaction to bacterial plaque present in the oral cavity.
- **Diabetes Mellitus**
- ✓ Diabetes mellitus is a common disorder of carbohydrate metabolism.

- ✓ This condition is associated with many oral manifestations; however, most of these are evident in patients who have poorly controlled insulin-dependent diabetes (IDDM or type 1 diabetes) than in those who are well-controlled with insulin or those with non insulin dependent diabetes (NIDDM or type 2 diabetes).⁽¹⁵⁾
- ✓ Postsurgical healing in these groups of patients is severely compromised and delayed.
- ✓ Delay in healing with subsequent increased accumulation of plaque and food debris, higher susceptibility to infections, and pronounced hyperplasia of attached gingiva all play a significant role in the increased incidence of periodontal disease in diabetics.
- ✓ A distinct type of erythematous gingiva with considerable degree of enlargement is noted as well.
- ✓ Diabetes- related periodontal abscesses are not uncommon
- ✓ Periodontal involvement is frequent and progresses at a faster pace than in the uninvolved patient.
- ✓ Diffuse, nontender, bilateral enlargement of the parotid glands, called diabetic sialadenosis may be noted in both types of diabetic.⁽²²⁾
- ✓ This condition is usually irreversible and even management of carbohydrate metabolism fails to restore the discrepancy.
- ✓ These patients are predisposed to a variety of oral candidal infections, usually presenting as a central papillary atrophy of the tongue dorsum in about 30% of these patients.
- ✓ Xerostomia or the subjective feeling of dry mouth is appreciated in one-third of the patient population, which may result from an overall diminished flow of saliva and an increased salivary glucose level.⁽²³⁾
- ✓ It has been well documented that there is a higher incidence of dental caries in patients with poorly controlled diabetes, which has been related to increased glucose levels in the saliva and the crevicular fluid.
- ✓ Dysgeusia or altered taste and burning mouth syndrome are frequently reported with poorly controlled diabetes.⁽²³⁾
- ✓ The dry mouth is a potential breeding ground and remains predisposed to the development of oral infections.
- ✓ Erythema migrans or geographic tongue is a finding noted more frequently in patients with type 1 diabetes than in the general population
- **Hypothyroidism (Cretinism, Myxedema)**
 - ✓ This condition is characterized by decreased levels of thyroid hormone.⁽¹⁵⁾
 - ✓ In infancy, this problem is termed cretinism.
 - ✓ In adulthood, the deficiency leads to marked deposition of glycosaminoglycans ground substance in the subcutaneous tissue, resulting in a nonpitting edema. This severe form of hypothyroidism is termed myxedema.
 - ✓ The lips appear swollen and generally thickened because of the glycosaminoglycans deposition.⁽²⁴⁾
 - ✓ Diffuse lingual enlargement is also appreciated. If the disease develops in early childhood, teeth fail to erupt but tooth formation proceeds at a normal pace.
- **Hyperthyroidism (Thyrotoxicosis, Graves' Disease)**
 - ✓ Hyperthyroidism is a condition characterized by excess production of thyroid hormone. This excess production markedly increases the metabolism of the affected patient.
 - ✓ Most of these changes are caused by Graves' disease. Other causes are hyperplasia of the thyroid gland tissue, and both benign and malignant thyroid tumors.

- ✓ The most common and obvious manifestation is the protrusion of the eyes termed exophthalmos or proptosis, also caused by the deposition of glycosaminoglycans in the retro-orbital tissues. ⁽²⁴⁾
- ✓ Other symptoms include nervousness, heart palpitations, heat intolerance, emotional lability, muscle weakness, and a warm smooth skin. ⁽²⁵⁾
- ✓ If the condition develops in early life or during tooth development, a pitting enamel hypoplasia and failure of tooth eruption may occur.
- **Hypoparathyroidism**
- ✓ Reduced amount of production of parathyroid hormone (PTH) is known as hypoparathyroidism, which usually results from surgical removal of the parathyroid glands during thyroidectomy for other reasons or from autoimmune destruction of the parathyroid tissue. ⁽²⁵⁾
- ✓ Rare syndromes such as DiGeorge syndrome and the endocrine-candidiasis syndrome may be associated with this condition.
- ✓ One of the main findings of loss of the parathyroid gland is hypocalcemia.
- ✓ Chvostek's sign is a significant oral finding that is marked by twitching of the upper lip when the facial nerve is tapped just below the zygomatic process. ⁽²⁵⁾
- ✓ If the condition develops in early life or during tooth development, a pitting enamel hypoplasia and failure of tooth eruption may occur. ⁽²⁶⁾
- **Hyperparathyroidism**
- ✓ Excess production of PTH results in the condition called hyperparathyroidism. ⁽²⁵⁾
- ✓ The patients present with the classic triad of "stones, bones, and abdominal groans." ⁽²⁵⁾
- ✓ Renal calculi as well as metastatic calcifications in the soft tissues can occur.
- ✓ Osseous changes.
- ✓ An early oral manifestation includes a radiographic presentation of generalized loss of the lamina dura of roots of teeth. The trabecular pattern of the bone is altered, resulting in a "ground-glass" appearance. ⁽²⁶⁾
- ✓ In the more advanced stages of the disease there is development of the so-called brown tumors of hyperparathyroidism, name derived from the color of the tissue specimen, which is dark reddish-brown due to the abundant hemorrhage and hemosiderin deposition within the tumor.
- ✓ Radiographically these are well-demarcated unilocular or multilocular radiolucencies. The mandible, clavicle, ribs, and pelvic bones are the frequent locations. Significant cortical expansion is not a rarity with long-standing lesions. ⁽²⁷⁾
- ✓ Abdominal groans refer to pain emanating from the tendency of development of duodenal ulcers.
- **Hypocortisolism (Cushing Syndrome)**
- ✓ Hypocortisolism, or Cushing syndrome, is a clinical condition that results from a sustained increase in blood glucocorticoid levels. ⁽²⁵⁾
- ✓ This syndrome mostly results from corticosteroid therapy prescribed for other medical conditions, or may be related to an endogenous source such as an adrenal or pituitary gland tumor or even overproduction from the adrenal gland.
- ✓ Oral manifestation includes prominent fatty tissue deposition in the facial area, resulting in a rounded facial appearance called "moon" facies. ⁽²⁵⁾

- ✓ A “buffalo hump” is noted, due to fat deposition in the dorsocervical spine region. There may be a variable degree of facial hirsutism noted on these patients.
- ✓ Osteoporosis leading to pathologic fractures of the mandible, maxilla, or alveolar bone as a result of trauma from impact may be a finding associated with this condition. ⁽²⁷⁾
- ✓ Poor tendency of wound healing results in delayed healing of fracture, alveolar bone, and soft tissues after dental extractions
- **Hypoadrenocorticism (Addison Disease)**
- ✓ Reduced or insufficient production of adrenal corticosteroid hormone is usually related to the destruction of the adrenal cortex, and results in a condition termed primary hypoadrenocorticism or Addison disease. ⁽²⁵⁾
- ✓ The striking orofacial manifestation is a “bronzing” hyperpigmentation of skin, noted on sun-exposed areas and also over pressure points. ⁽¹⁵⁾
- ✓ This appearance is directly related to increased levels of b-lipotropin or ACTH, which stimulates melanocytes, in turn leading to the bronzing effect.
- ✓ Other oral presentations include a diffuse or patchy brown macular pigmentation most commonly on the buccal mucosa as well as on the floor of the mouth, ventral tongue, and other areas of the oral mucosa. The oral mucosal presentation often is the first manifestation of the disease and precedes the skin changes. ⁽²⁵⁾

DERMATOLOGIC DISEASES

- ✓ In number of dermatologic diseases, oral manifestations appear alone or prior to the general skin changes. The environment of the oral cavity is subject to significant local irritation and thus may present the most significant signs and symptoms of the condition.
- **Lichen planus**
- ✓ Lichen planus (LP) is a chronic inflammatory cutaneous disease that frequently involves oral mucosa.
- ✓ It affects 0.5-2.0% of the population with a predilection for women and a mean age of onset in the fourth to fifth decade. ⁽¹⁵⁾
- ✓ The oral manifestations of lichen planus may occur weeks or months before the appearance of the skin lesions.
- ✓ Bilateral lesional distribution is a key diagnostic feature⁽¹⁵⁾
- ✓ Oral lesions are characterized by small whitish hyperkeratotic papules whose arrangement makes up the typical linear, annular and reticular thread like patterns. Other oral lesions have been described as plaque like, papular, pigmented, verrucous or hypertrophic, atrophic, erosive or ulcerative and vesiculo-bullous.
- **Psoriasis**
- ✓ Characterized by angular cheilosis, fissured tongue and benign migratory glossitis. ⁽¹⁵⁾
- ✓ Lesions involve the lips, buccal mucosa, palate, gingival and floor of the mouth and appear as gray or yellowish-white plaques; as silvery white, scaly lesions with an erythematous base.
- ✓ Also seen as multiple papular eruptions, which may be ulcerated; or as small, papillary, elevated lesions with a scaly surface.
- **Erythema multiforme**
- ✓ Oral manifestations include hyperemic macules, papules or vesicles, which may become eroded or ulcerated and bleed freely.
- ✓ The tongue, palate, buccal mucosa and gingival are commonly involved. ⁽²⁸⁾

- ✓ Lips and anterior part of oral cavity are frequently affected.
- ✓ Oral lesions are manifested as a bullae, erosions or ulcers, which may or may not be covered by pseudomembrane.
- ✓ Target lesions are usually seen involving lip.
- ✓ Vermillion border of lip presents as characteristic bloody crusted appearance
- ✓ Gingival is rarely involved, while the lesion heal without scarring.

- ✓ Stevens Johnsons syndrome: Oral lesions may be extremely severe and so painful that mastication is impossible.
- ✓ Mucosal vesicles or bullae occur which rupture and leaves surfaces covered with a thick white or yellow exudate.⁽²⁸⁾
- ✓ The lips may exhibit ulcerations with bloody crusting and are painful.
- **Pemphigus**
- ✓ PV is a serious autoimmune disorder with mucocutaneous manifestations characterized by the development of intraepithelial blisters on the skin and/or mucosal membranes.⁽¹⁵⁾
- ✓ PV usually manifests between the fourth and fifth decades of life, and affects both males and females equally.
- ✓ The lesions consist of small and asymptomatic blisters that rupture easily, giving rise to painful and bleeding erosions.
- ✓ While any part of the oral cavity can be affected, the most common locations are the friction zones such as the cheek mucosa, tongue, palate, lower lip and gums.
- ✓ The lesions typically develop over several months in the oral cavity before spreading to the skin and other mucosal zones such as the pharynx, larynx, esophagus or genital mucosa.
- ✓ The bullae tend to rupture as soon as they form.
- ✓ The oral mucosa also exhibits Nikolsky's phenomenon and may be denuded by the peripheral enlargement of the erosions.⁽¹⁵⁾
- ✓ Lesions are tender, bleed easily have ragged border and be covered by a white or blood tinged exudate.
- ✓ Extension onto the lips with the production of crusting may occur. There may be profuse salivation, and the stench is overwhelming
- **Cicatricial pemphigoid**
- ✓ MMP is a chronic autoimmune disease of unknown etiology that manifests in the form of subepithelial blisters.⁽¹⁵⁾
- ✓ Classically, the variants of MMP are bullous pemphigoid and mucous membrane or cicatricial pemphigoid – the latter being the most common presentation.
- ✓ It is more common in females, and the mean age at onset of the disease is in the fifth or sixth decade of life.
- ✓ Characterized by vesiculobullous lesions, which are relatively thick walled and, may persist for 24 to 48 hours before rupturing and desquamating
- ✓ When rupture they leave a raw, eroded, bleeding surface.
- ✓ The gingival appears to be erythematous for weeks or even months after the original erosions have healed
- ✓ Within the oral cavity, the most frequently affected locations are the gums, followed by the soft and hard palate, the oral mucosa and the tongue.

- ✓ Clinically, the affected patients show blisters occupying the full thickness of the epithelium, and which can develop for hours or days before rupturing.
- ✓ When these blisters finally rupture, they leave pseudomembranes with irregularly shaped yellowish ulcerations surrounded by an erythematous halo.
- ✓ A positive Nikolsky's sign is a common finding. Bleeding, pain and desquamation of the oral mucosa may occur.
- ✓ Occasionally, gingival inflammation in the absence of bacterial plaque can be observed, in the form of chronic desquamative gingivitis.
- ✓ Ocular involvement is also a characteristic of Cicatricial pemphigoid termed as 'Symblepheron'.⁽²⁹⁾

PSYCHIATRIC DISORDERS

▪ Anorexia & bulimia nervosa

- ✓ The dentists and dental hygienists may be the first health care providers to assess the physical and oral effects of anorexia nervosa and bulimia nervosa.
- ✓ The oral manifestations include dental erosion, traumatized oral mucosal membranes and pharynx, dry mouth, dental caries, periodontal disease, and soft tissue lesions.⁽³⁰⁾
- ✓ More specifically, dental erosion involves lingual erosion on the palatal surfaces of the maxillary teeth with a smooth, glossy appearance and increased tooth sensitivity.
- ✓ This erosion is characterized by loss of enamel with rounded margins, a notched appearance of the incisal surfaces of the anterior teeth, amalgam restorations that appear as raised islands, and loss of contours on unrestored teeth.⁽³⁰⁾
- ✓ Self-induced vomiting may cause trauma to the soft palate and pharynx.
- ✓ Soft tissue lesions such as angular cheilitis, candidosis, glossitis, and oral mucosal ulceration may also occur from nutritional deficiencies.

NEOPLASTIC CONDITIONS

▪ Metastatic Disease

- ✓ Metastatic tumors to the oral region are rare but may involve both the soft and/or hard tissues, and comprise about 1% of oral malignant neoplasms.⁽²⁵⁾
- ✓ These metastatic lesions are noted more often to the jaws than to oral soft tissue.
- ✓ Breast carcinoma is the most commonly metastasizing tumor to the jaws, whereas lung carcinomas commonly go for the oral soft tissues.⁽³¹⁾
- ✓ The most common bony site for metastasis is the molar region of the mandible and in almost one-third of reported cases; the oral metastatic lesion is the initial finding of the undiscovered malignancy.
- ✓ The most common site for oral soft tissue metastasis is the gingiva, and this site alone accounts for over 25% of all cases
- ✓ The lesions appear more like common hyperplastic reactive lesions of the gingiva, mimicking a pyogenic granuloma that is often ulcerated.
- ✓ Adjacent teeth may be loosened due to concomitant destruction of the underlying bone.

- ✓ These soft tissue metastases are more common in males than in females, and require a biopsy for definitive diagnosis.
- ✓ Metastatic tumors to the jaws are detected when the patient presents with swelling, pain, paresthesia, and even with what is termed as the “numb-chin syndrome,” which is often noted when the lesion involves the mental nerve.⁽³²⁾
- ✓ Radiographically these metastatic lesions are ill-defined radiolucencies with ragged, jagged, or irregular borders and sometimes may be mixed, both radiolucent and radiopaque in presentation.
- ✓ Although rare, the possibility of an oral metastatic lesion should always be considered in cases of unexplained oral cavity growths or jaw radiolucencies.

CONCLUSION

The oral cavity is a portal of entry as well as the site of disease for microbial infections that affect general health status. As discussed, many systemic diseases and conditions have oral manifestations.

Often oral manifestations are the first sign or the most significant sign of systemic disease. Dentists must acquire familiarity with systemic conditions that can affect the oral cavity, so that appropriate referral can be made. Thus, mouth presents a window for easy observation of signs and symptoms of many systemic diseases.

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